
Mapping mobility project

Data management plan (V2)

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This document outlines the data that will be collected through the Mapping Mobility project and the subsequent collection, description, storage and access to the data therein.

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1. Collection of data:

There are three distinctive data types within this project, which are new, digital data:

Mobility data – This is spatially referenced data pertaining to an individual's change in location over time.

- The data is collected through the application MapMyTracks and is exported in the .GPX format as vector data.
- Approximately 2 TB of this data will be collected.

Qualitative data – Transcripts - collected through training and analytical workshops with contributors and citizen scientists.

- This data is collected through engagement in the citizen science programme and allows us to evaluate the effectiveness of the training process.
- Approximately 500mb of this data will be collected.

Participant data – This includes the participants real name (if a citizen scientist), their account name in Map My Tracks, their status in the project (i.e. contributor or citizen scientist) and the data contributions they have made within the project. Participants must consent to take part.

Data quality for all data types is evaluated through ongoing maintenance processes by the research team.

2. Storage, security, and backup:

There is a simple 4 stage process:

1. Data is exported to us via app developers Tinderhouse. This will be per 'account' and will contain any contributions this participant has made.
2. Data will initially be stored on a secure hard drive, which is only accessed by the research team.

3. At this stage, all data types undergo processes of anonymization:

Participant data: Participants will be identified through their randomised account name on Map My Tracks, which will act as the link between their data contributions.

Mobility data: location data is assigned an “FID”, i.e. 1,2 or 46, which marks it as an entry within our database (figure 1). This is assigned to the anonymous user account that submitted it and the date it was submitted (for retrieval purposes if required later).

Qualitative data: participants are assigned a pseudonym, thus anonymizing identities.

4. Data is then uploaded to the “main” data table (figure 2). This enables us to locate necessary data and keep track of contributions.

This data is backed up bi-weekly.

It is stored on a password protected hard drive.

3. Archiving, preservation, and curation:

Data is initially stored via the following tables (figure 1 and figure 2).

List of contributions:		
FID	Submitted by (username):	Date submitted:
1	ACTION7	05/05/21
2	ACTION7	08/05/21
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8		
9		
10		
11		
12		

Figure 1: The data anonymization process for mobility data.

Once the data has been anonymised it is added to a main password protected database. Here, the identities of the participants, the contributions they have made, their account identities and the degree of involvement in the project.

Contributer ID	Username:	Ethics forms received?	Contributions (FIDs):	Full Identity:	Contributer or citizen scientist?	Attended Training workshop 1?	Attended Training workshop 2?	Attended Training workshop 3?
Example	ACTION7	Yes	1,4,5,26	John smith	Citizen scientist	Yes	Yes	Yes
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								

Figure 2: The main password protected data base.

Once anonymization has been completed, the data is uploaded to the ACTION website, which serves as an open repository for data in the long term.

4. Discovery, access, sharing and metadata:

Data will be published with a creative commons license.

There are no ethical issues that arise as the data has been anonymised.

Data is posted in .GPX and .CSV formats.

5. Rights and responsibilities:

This data management plan will be adhered to by the principle investigator Zoe Robinson, Co-investigator, Adam Peacock and the Graduate Researcher, TBD.

Data will be copyrighted by Keele University.